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SUMMARY

This deliverable report presents the technical and functional analysis, prototyping, and development of the digital tools designed within Work Package 6 of the NOVAFOODIES project. The focus is on the creation and implementation of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform and the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App, developed to enhance transparency and traceability in the fish and aquaculture supply chains. These tools play a central role in achieving the project's objectives of increasing consumer trust and promoting sustainable practices.

The NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace is a cloud-based B2B platform that enables producers and wholesale buyers to exchange data and manage processes in a transparent, secure, and efficient manner. The system integrates traceability information, quality and biosecurity, and supports the tracking of production batches and shipments through QR codes and RFID tags. Real-time data is collected via IoT devices developed by ITENE and stored immutably using blockchain technology, ensuring accuracy and reliability across the value chain.

Alongside the platform, the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App was developed to empower end users by providing access to product traceability in a simple and intuitive way. By scanning the QR code available in stores, consumers can consult detailed and verified information on the product's origin, production practices, certifications, nutritional properties, and environmental parameters, without the need to provide personal data.

The pilot cases implementation of these tools is currently underway, thanks to the collaboration with partner aquaculture producers in Italy and Greece. The experimental phase involves their sales networks and the consumers of their seafood products, marking a key step toward validating the system and promoting a more transparent, traceable, and sustainable European aquaculture sector.

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INTRODUCTION

The traceability of fishery and aquaculture products plays a crucial role in ensuring food safety, combating fraud, and supporting the sustainability of the sector. While European regulations such as Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 and its implementing measures set the legal framework for traceability, the NOVAFOODIES project aims to go further. It introduces a deeper, voluntary and digital traceability model, capable of building trust among consumers and offering added value for producers along the seafood supply chain.

Within Work Package 6, this deliverable describes the design and development of a digital ecosystem composed of two complementary tools: the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace and the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App. These tools have been co-developed with aquaculture producers in Italy and Greece, aiming to empower the entire supply chain—from farmers to consumers—with transparent, real-time, and verifiable information, in line with the objectives of the EU Farm to Fork strategy.

The tools have been designed and developed by INFOTEAM, a digital SME with more than 10 years of experience in cloud solutions, mobile apps, and traceability systems in the fisheries sector.

1.1. Objectives

The main objective of this activity within Work Package 6 is to design and implement digital tools that enhance transparency, traceability, and trust along the fish and aquaculture value chains. Specifically, the project aims to develop an online B2B MarketPlace platform for fish and aquaculture products, offering a high-tech solution for at least 100 producers and wholesale operators. The platform includes data on traceability, quality parameters, and biosecurity assessments, supporting the introduction of innovative and sustainable products into the European market.

In parallel, a user-friendly mobile application has been developed to provide end-consumers with direct access to traceability information. By simply scanning a QR code, users can view verified details about the origin, certifications, environmental parameters, and nutritional values of the seafood products they purchase. The app, which requires no personal data to function, aims to reach and engage at least 1,000 consumers, helping to build confidence in the transparency and reliability of the seafood supply chain.

During the first months of the project, it was verified that no project partners were in a position to offer a pilot case based on traditional fishery supply chains. However, since several NOVAFOODIES partners operate aquaculture farms and are involved in trials on Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) systems, the project consortium—under the coordination of the Lead Partner IDENER—agreed to adapt the pilot case to this alternative but highly relevant context.

Our first initiative was also to use our RFID technology for algae cultivation-production (biomasses) traceability, as written in Task 6.2 was to involve all major fish auction in Cadiz (Spain) coast to provide accurate estimates regarding biomass availability. However, this latter activity did not materialise due to a lack of concrete engagement from the local stakeholders and logistical constraints. Subsequently, we had the opportunity to collaborate with two real companies (one in Italy and one in Greece) with mass production series that are involved in the aquacultural sector.

Thus, we decided to change the location of our pilot cases as well as the type of products that are tracked by our technologies.

Nevertheless, the core goals and expected outcomes remain unchanged, while the focus shifts from fishery to aquaculture, maintaining full alignment with the objectives defined in the Grant Agreement.

This adjustment allows the project not only to continue its activities with strong operational relevance, but also to demonstrate traceability innovations in a context that reflects the future of sustainable seafood production in Europe.

2. SEAFOOD TRACEABILITY ASSESSMENT

Before designing and developing the digital tools foreseen in the NOVAFOODIES project, it was essential to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current landscape of seafood traceability. This preliminary phase aimed to understand the existing practices and EU regulations governing traceability in the fish and aquaculture sectors and to identify the real needs and challenges faced by aquaculture producers.

The analysis focused on several key aspects: the state of the art in food quality and biosecurity monitoring, the digitalization level of seafood traceability systems, and the main requirements expressed by stakeholders during dedicated meeting and surveys. Special attention was also given to the most recent ISO standards, as well as to the emergence of innovative technologies such as IoT, blockchain, RFID, and QR-based systems, which are increasingly being applied to enhance transparency and trust in the seafood value chain.

2.1. Traceability information, quality and biosecurity

In the early phases of WP6 activities, a structured analysis was carried out to identify all the information needed to implement a complete, transparent, and reliable traceability system for fish and aquaculture products. The goal was to go beyond the legal traceability requirements established by European regulations, by designing a data model capable of increasing consumer trust and enhancing the perceived quality of seafood products.

To achieve this, the team collected and analysed a wide range of data categories relevant to the entire supply chain—from production to distribution. These include information on species, origin, production sites, farming methods, harvest or processing dates, certifications, batch identification, and shipment tracking. Additionally, input was gathered directly from aquaculture producers involved in the pilot activities, who helped define key parameters based on their operational needs and sustainability goals.

The pilot phase involved close collaboration with the selected partners Aqua de Ma [A.P. of UNIGE] and Kefalonia Fisheries [KEFISH], through online interviews and targeted surveys aimed at gathering specific operational needs, traceability practices, and expectations for the digital tools to be tested and used.

The survey was designed to gather detailed and context-specific information directly from the partners involved in the pilot cases, with the aim of supporting the functional design of the NOVAFOODIES traceability system. The structure of the questionnaire followed the main stages of

the production cycle and related data domains: Producer Registry, Product Registry, Production Site Registry, Seeding Registry, Batch Registry, Nutrients, Certifications or Reports, Market Registry, and Monthly Batch Delivery.

Each question was formulated as open-ended, allowing partners to provide elaborated and unrestricted feedback. This qualitative approach enabled the collection of rich and realistic insights, reflecting the operational complexity and specific needs of the aquaculture companies involved.

The responses were then discussed and validated through follow-up online interviews with each partner. These interviews served to clarify any ambiguities, confirm the accuracy of the data provided, and collect additional elements useful for the system's design and customization.

Table 1 – Brief Report: Survey for recordset and value chain for Aquaculture - Seafood products.

Type of information	Question	Aqua de M à	Kefalonia Fisheries
PRODUCER REGISTRY	What are complete information about the company?	Information about: off-shore mariculture plant located offshore of the coast of Lavagna and Orosei plants....	Information about: continuous improvement of production techniques , the development of sustainable practices and the welfare of fish....
PRODUCTS REGISTRY	Which fish species?	Seabass (BSS) Dicentrarchus labrax Seabream (SBG) Sparus aurata	Seabass BSS (Dicentrarchus Labrax), Seabream SBG (Sparus aurata)
PRODUCTION SITE REGISTRY	What kind of information about single plant?	Lavagna/off-shore/ 400T Orosei/off-shore/350T	Complete geo coordinates about Kefalonia plant: capacity: 2.500T
SEEDING REGISTRY	What kind of information about seeding and growing?	Growing the fish from the seed size (5 grams) to the fishing size (360 grams) and lasts approximately 18 – 24 months	We introduce fry almost every month, with 2 yearly generations (BS 24.01 and BS 24.02)
BATCH REGISTRY	What is the batch format?	The batch identifies all the fry seed inside a single cage. Ex.: LOT BR0223 BR 02 23	Ongrowing site and packing plant we have a number indicated the specific cage, Example: BS 000226 , (s.bass from cage 226) The same for sea bream.

NUTRIENTS	Do you have a datasheet or label? Certificates of laboratory?	Yes , see Technical datasheet	YES , we keep nutritional info from lab, not on the label.
CERTIFICATION or REPORTS	Do you have other kind of certification or compliant report? GMO-Free, Antibiotic-Free, or Environmental protection, ISO certification...etc	Yes , certification for Antibiotic-Free and SQNZ Sustainable Aquaculture	Yes , ISO 14000, ISO 9000, GLOBAL GAP, FRIEND OF THE SEA
MARKET REGISTRY	How many types of distributors/retailers do you include in the pilot case? (GDO, gross dealer, store)	n. 1 GDO with n.52 total retail stores	90% exported in Europe, USA and UAE. Super markets, fish mongers and wholesaler distributors. No numbers.
BATCH DELIVERY EACH MONTH	How many new batches of products do you deliver to different clients involved in the pilot case each month?	Seabass (BSS) , each month: n. 12 Seabream (SBG) , each month: n. 12	N.A.

The analysis of the survey played a key role in guiding the design of the NOVAFOODIES traceability system, as it served a dual purpose. On one hand, it aimed to understand which data were already available and easily accessible by each aquaculture producer. On the other, it focused on identifying the essential data required to ensure transparent, complete, and trustworthy traceability for each individual farmer’s supply chain.

By examining the responses, the project team was able to map the current practices, gaps, and capabilities of the two pilot partners in documenting traceability information—from batch registration to environmental parameters and certifications. This helped to distinguish between data that could be collected automatically (e.g. via sensors or existing reports) and those that required manual input, thus highlighting opportunities to streamline the process.

At the same time, the survey analysis supported the search for a shared and standardized data structure, which is critical to making the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform efficient and scalable. The goal was to define a common format that reduces the effort required from producers, avoiding unnecessary complexity while still enabling the system to deliver high-quality traceability information to consumers. This approach balances flexibility and standardization, ensuring that producers of different sizes and digital maturity can participate in the platform with minimal barriers, while maintaining the integrity and completeness of the traceability data.

The interviews also revealed a strong willingness among aquaculture producers to obtain not only process-related certifications, but also environmental sustainability certifications. This reflects their clear commitment to sustainable aquaculture practices and their intention to make this effort visible and recognizable to the public, as a key element in building trust and differentiating their products in the market.

Particular attention was given to the integration of biosecurity assessment data. These indicators, derived from sensors and monitoring protocols, include environmental and health-related parameters such as water temperature, oxygen levels, presence of ammonia or pathogens, and compliance with hygiene practices. By incorporating this information into the digital traceability system, it is possible to provide end-users not only with the traditional traceability data, but also with insights on the sanitary conditions and environmental sustainability of the production process.

This comprehensive approach contributes to strengthening the link between producers and consumers, allowing the final user to make informed decisions based on clear, trustworthy, and value-added information about the seafood they consume.

2.2. Seafood traceability rules

Traceability is a core requirement in ensuring food safety, product integrity, and consumer trust in the aquaculture sector. In the European Union, the regulatory framework for the traceability of fishery and aquaculture products is defined by several key legal texts that establish the obligations for all operators involved in the supply chain—from production to retail.

The main reference is Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009, which establishes a control system for ensuring compliance with the Common Fisheries Policy. Article 58 of this regulation requires that all lots of fishery and aquaculture products be traceable at all stages of production, processing, and distribution. Operators must be able to identify both the supplier and the buyer of any given batch and must store this information for a minimum of five years.

Complementing this, Implementing Regulation (EU) No 404/2011 outlines the specific data that must be recorded, including:

- Commercial designation and scientific name of the species;
- Production method (e.g., caught at sea, caught in freshwater, or farmed);
- Country of origin and harvest area;
- Category of fishing gear used (for wild-caught fish);
- Lot identification and quantity;
- Supplier and recipient details.

In addition, Regulation (EU) No 1379/2013 on the common organisation of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products reinforces the requirement for accurate consumer information at the point of sale. This includes the obligation to display details about the product's commercial name, production method, catch or farming area, and, optionally, sustainability certifications or eco-labels.

However, these regulations mostly focus on legal compliance and food safety, while the NOVAFOODIES project aims to go beyond by integrating voluntary traceability information related to quality, environmental monitoring, and biosecurity—adding value and transparency for both producers and consumers.

The design of the traceability features within the NOVAFOODIES Market Place platform and mobile application was also inspired by the publication *“A pocket guide to the EU’s new fish and aquaculture consumer labels”* (European Commission, 2014). This guide outlines the mandatory information required on labels for fishery and aquaculture products placed on the EU market as well as recommendations on how to clearly communicate this information to consumers. Building on these guidelines, label for NOVAFOODIES App integrates all mandatory fields and further enriches the consumer interface with additional voluntary data on quality, sustainability, and environmental impact, thus promoting informed and responsible seafood consumption.

Figure 1 - A pocket guide to the EU’s new fish and aquaculture consumer labels

Beyond the European regulatory framework, international guidelines also play a crucial role in shaping traceability practices in the aquaculture and seafood sectors. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) provides comprehensive guidance to support countries and producers in implementing robust traceability systems.

In particular, the FAO Guidelines for the Ecolabelling of Fish and Fishery Products and the FAO Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries encourage the adoption of traceability mechanisms that cover not only the movement of products along the supply chain but also aspects such as:

- Environmental sustainability
- Animal health and welfare
- Social responsibility and fair labour practices

- Prevention of IUU (Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated) fishing

The FAO also recommends the use of digital technologies—including RFID, barcodes, and blockchain systems—to enhance the efficiency, accuracy, and transparency of traceability systems, particularly in complex international supply chains.

These international recommendations complement the EU regulatory context and provide strategic direction for projects like NOVAFOODIES, which aim to raise the traceability standard beyond minimum legal compliance, aligning with global expectations for sustainable and ethical aquaculture.

2.3. Aquaculture traceability needs

Through the interviews and surveys conducted with the pilot partners Aqua de Ma (Italy) and Kefalonia Fisheries (Greece), a shared set of traceability needs clearly emerged, reflecting the specific characteristics of their production systems, distribution networks, and market positioning. Both companies operate in the fresh aquaculture segment, delivering high-quality products—primarily sea bass and sea bream—to national and international markets. Their distribution channels include wholesale, retail, and direct-to-store delivery, often in collaboration with long-standing commercial partners.

While both producers already comply with the traceability obligations established by EU legislation, they expressed a strong interest in going beyond the legal minimum by **adopting a voluntary digital traceability system**. This system should be capable of capturing and displaying additional quality and sustainability indicators, in order to respond to evolving consumer expectations and differentiate their offer on the market.

The common needs identified include:

- Completing the legally required traceability with an additional, separate layer of information, accessible to both business partners and consumers.
- Highlighting the quality of their products through transparent, verifiable, and easily accessible data.
- Making their supply chain more transparent to end users, showcasing the care and standardization behind every production stage.
- Giving visibility to certifications and production protocols, such as those related to environmental sustainability, OMG free and antibiotic free growing.
- Enhancing brand positioning by building a narrative of trust and responsibility around their aquaculture practices.
- Ensuring simplicity and efficiency, by implementing a system that minimizes the extra workload for both internal staff and external partners, while still delivering high added value.

These insights have guided the technical and functional design of the NOVAFOODIES Marketplace and Mobile App, which were developed to be modular, easy to use, and adaptable to real-world operational needs, while supporting the broader goals of transparency, traceability, and sustainable seafood value chains in Europe. Currently, there is no product or system available on the market that can transparently trace aquaculture products in this way, making this a unique opportunity for producers to increase the visibility of their brand, position themselves in a higher-value market

segment, and strengthen their reputation for commitment to safe and environmentally sustainable practices.

2.4. Digital traceability in aquaculture sector

Digital traceability in the aquaculture sector is increasingly recognized as a vital component for ensuring food safety, sustainability, and consumer trust. While the European Union has established foundational regulations, such as Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EU) No 1379/2013, which mandate basic traceability requirements, these frameworks primarily focus on batch-level tracking and do not encompass comprehensive, real-time digital monitoring across the entire production and distribution chain.

To address these limitations, international standards have been developed to support more advanced traceability models. ISO 22005:2007 outlines general principles for designing and implementing traceability systems in the food and feed chain, while ISO 12875:2011 specifically addresses traceability of captured finfish, offering potential applications for aquaculture. More recently, ISO 23455:2022 has introduced functional requirements for utilizing blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) in cold chain traceability, providing a robust foundation for digital applications in seafood logistics.

In the realm of research and innovation, several EU-funded projects have explored digital traceability solutions for seafood. The FishEUTrust project, for instance, aims to enhance trust in EU fish supply chains by integrating genomic tools and blockchain data systems to foster traceability and authenticity of seafood products. Similarly, the SEA2SEE project focuses on developing an end-to-end blockchain-based platform to address existing seafood traceability gaps, thereby increasing trust and social acceptance of sustainably fished and farmed seafood.

The EU co-funded TRUST-FOOD project is actively working to equip professionals also in the food sector with the necessary skills to implement digital traceability systems. By offering specialized training courses focused on blockchain technology and its applications within the food supply chain, the project aims to enhance transparency, safety, and trust across the industry. These courses are tailored to meet the needs of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), providing practical knowledge to support the adoption of advanced digital tools for traceability.

Despite these advancements, practical implementations of comprehensive digital traceability systems in aquaculture remain limited. Existing solutions often concentrate on specific stages of the supply chain or are tailored for export compliance, lacking the integration of real-time environmental monitoring and direct consumer accessibility.

Figure 2 - Digital traceability for biomass and seafood supply chain

In this context, the NOVAFOODIES project represents a significant advancement by demonstrating how digital tools can combine legal compliance with voluntary transparency measures. By integrating IoT sensors, blockchain technology, and mobile interfaces, the project aims to provide end-to-end traceability from farm to consumer, thereby enhancing the value proposition of aquaculture products through clear, accessible, and verifiable information.

2.5. Blockchain technologies in seafood value chains

Blockchain technology is increasingly recognized as a transformative tool for enhancing transparency, traceability, and trust within food value chains. Its decentralized and immutable nature allows for secure recording of transactions and product histories, which is particularly beneficial in complex supply chains like those in the food industry.

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations has highlighted the potential of blockchain to address challenges in agri-food systems, including improving supply chain integration, enhancing food safety, and increasing market transparency. By facilitating the secure sharing of information among stakeholders, blockchain can help ensure compliance with international agreements and support sustainable development goals.

Two key reference documents published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations provide valuable insight into the use of blockchain and digital traceability systems in seafood value chains.

The publication “Blockchain Application in Seafood Value Chains” (FAO, 2020) offers a comprehensive overview of how blockchain can be applied to support transparency, legality, and trust in fisheries and aquaculture. It explores the core concepts of Critical Tracking Events (CTEs) and Key Data Elements (KDEs) as the foundation for traceability, and presents case studies demonstrating how blockchain can combat fraud, improve seafood safety, and ensure product authenticity. While highlighting the advantages of blockchain—including immutability and decentralized verification—the document also discusses its operational challenges, such as regulatory uncertainty, implementation costs, and technological barriers in small-scale contexts.

Complementing this, the “Guidance Document: Advancing End-to-End Traceability – Critical Tracking Events and Key Data Elements along Capture Fisheries and Aquaculture Value Chains” (FAO, 2023) provides a practical framework for developing digital traceability systems across the seafood supply chain. It emphasizes the importance of standardized CTEs and KDEs and promotes the adoption of interoperable, electronic traceability systems. The guidance also reflects a global consensus on the need for integrated, cross-border traceability systems that are inclusive and adaptable to both regulatory and voluntary traceability goals.

Together, these documents establish a solid foundation for designing reliable and scalable digital traceability systems in the seafood sector, and they have served as strategic references for the NOVAFOODIES project in aligning its technical solutions with internationally recognized best practices.

To support the implementation of blockchain in food supply chains, several international standards have been developed:

- ISO 22739:2020: This standard provides fundamental terminology for blockchain and distributed ledger technologies, establishing a common vocabulary to facilitate understanding and communication among stakeholders.
- ISO/TS 23635:2022: This technical specification offers guiding principles and a framework for the governance of blockchain and distributed ledger technology systems, addressing aspects such as decision rights, responsibilities, and accountability.
- ISO/TR 6039:2023: This technical report provides an overview of identifiers for subjects and objects in the design of blockchain systems, facilitating interoperability between blockchain and non-blockchain systems.
- ISO/TR 16340:2023: Focusing on cold chain food, this report addresses the application of blockchain-based traceability platforms to ensure continuous and effective tracking throughout the food's lifecycle, enhancing data integrity and supply chain collaboration.

Traceability in the cold chain for food is essential in ensuring food safety, through which continuous tracking of the whole lifecycle is realized, including cold chain food production, storage, purchase, sales, and transportation, etc. In ISO/TR 16340:2023, a blockchain-based traceability platform is proposed, which links the required data series throughout the circulation of the cold chain food. By applying such a platform, the following benefits are expected:

- anti-counterfeiting: on this platform, each batch of cold chain food in the container is identified by a unique code, which can enable identification of each distinct batch of cold chain food;

- trusted lifecycle tracking: the information throughout the circulation of the cold chain food is written into the blockchain, which is tamper-resistant; and identity cannot be denied;
- supply chain collaboration: the traceability data are shared among the supply chain by leveraging distribution databases/records/ledgers to achieve unified credentials and reduce logistics costs;
- effective regulation: the platform provides credentials for regulatory agencies, and the most important information about cold chain food safety for consumers.

These standards collectively contribute to the establishment of robust blockchain applications in food value chains, promoting transparency, efficiency, and consumer trust.

3. NOVAFOODIES MARKET PLACE DESIGN

The NOVAFOODIES Marketplace platform was designed to support digital traceability in aquaculture through a modular and cloud-based system. It integrates data from IoT sensors for freshness and GPS position monitoring, RFID tags for shipment tracking, and blockchain technology to ensure secure and immutable traceability records. The platform allows producers to register batches, sites, and shipments, and automatically generates QR code labels for consumer access. The system is user-friendly, supports real-time data sharing via APIs.

The UI/UX design of the MarketPlace platform prioritizes simplicity and clarity for producers and distributors. A dedicated dashboard allows users to register products, batches, customers, and shipments, with traceability labels generated automatically for printing and display in stores. QR code labels link directly to the blockchain-backed data, ensuring transparency for end consumers.

3.1. IoT device API data integration and communication

The communication protocol for integrating the IoT device with the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform was jointly designed by INFOTEAM and ITENE, ensuring alignment between technical feasibility and functional requirements defined during the design phase. This close collaboration made it possible to create a lightweight and efficient data exchange mechanism tailored to the needs of just-in-time monitoring in aquaculture logistics.

The integration with the Novafoodies platform enhances user experience by offering a centralized interface for managing data, analysing trends, and receiving alerts for critical gas levels.

The IoT device, designed by ITENE (*D6.4 Novel traceability system for value chains*), collects a set of critical environmental and freshness-related parameters. The system captures the following measurements:

1. Timestamp of the measurement
2. Temperature (ambient and product-specific)
3. Humidity (ambient relative humidity)
4. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels
5. Geolocation (GPS coordinates) of the device
6. Ammonia (NH₃) concentration
7. Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) levels
8. Methane (CH₄) concentration

These data are transmitted via secure HTTP requests to the NOVAFOODIES cloud infrastructure, where they are automatically linked to the corresponding production batch and stored for analysis.

Integrating our server with IoT devices aims to simplify and secure communication between devices.

Follow a breakdown of the API structure:

- “date”: This string indicates the exact date and time when the measurements were taken. It follows the format "YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM".
- “temperature”: This numerical value represents the temperature in degrees Celsius, ranging from -40°C to 100°C.
- “humidity”: This value indicates the relative humidity as a percentage, ranging from 0% to 100% relative humidity.
- “CO2”: This integer denotes the concentration of carbon dioxide in parts per million (ppm), ranging from 400 to 10.000 ppm.
- “GPS”: This object contains two properties:
 - “latitude”: A decimal number representing the geographic latitude of the device's location, ranging from -90° to 90°.
 - “longitude”: A decimal number representing the geographic longitude of the device's location, ranging from -180° to 180°.
- “NH3”: This value indicates the concentration of ammonia (NH3) in ppm, ranging from 0 to 100 ppm.
- “H2S”: This number represents the concentration of hydrogen sulfide (H2S) in ppm, ranging from 0 to 100 ppm.
- “CH4”: This value signifies the concentration of methane (CH4) in ppm, ranging from 400 to 25.000 ppm.

the necessary steps for enrolling devices, authenticating, and renewing tokens to gain access to protected APIs. Prior to starting the integration process, it's important to ensure that the following requirements are met: Before proceeding with the integration, ensure you have the following requirements:

- A unique deviceId must be assigned to each IoT device, represented as a string.
- An apiKey is required, which is provided during the vendor verification process. This key is static and remains valid across all devices that need to be enrolled.

Enrolling IoT devices marks the first step in integrating with the server. The process involves making two key API calls:

Enrollment Call - Used to register the device in the system. It is necessary to include the following parameters in the body of the request:

- deviceId (string): the unique identifier of the device.
- apiKey (string): the API key shared during the verification process.

Example of an enrollment request:

```
POST /api/v1/auth/enrollment
Host: server.example.com
Content-Type: application/json
{
  "deviceId": "<Unique device ID>",
  "apiKey": "<Secret API Key>"
}
```

Figure 3 - API example of an enrolment request

Example of a confirmation response:

```
{
  "success": true,
  "message": "Enrolled successfully"
}
```

Figure 4 - API example of a confirmation response

Login Call - Once enrolment is complete, make a login call to obtain the access token and refresh token. These tokens are essential for authenticating subsequent API calls.

Example of a login request:

```
POST /api/v1/auth/login
Host: server.example.com
Content-Type: application/json
{
  "deviceId": "<Unique device ID>",
  "apiKey": "<Secret API Key>"
}
```

Figure 5 - API example of a login request

Example of a success response:

```
{
  "access_token": "xxx",
  "refresh_token": "yyy",
  "deviceId": "1"
}
```

Example of an error response. Device not enrolled:

```
{
  "statusCode": 401,
  "message": "Device not enrolled",
  "timestamp": "2024-02-24T13:31:49.900Z",
  "path": "/api/v1/auth/login"
}
```

Figure 6 - API example of a success and error responses

After enrolment, for each call to protected APIs, it is necessary to authenticate using the obtained access token. The access token should be included in the headers of the requests in the following way: *Authorization: Bearer {{ACCESS_TOKEN}}*

When the access token expires, it is possible to obtain a new token by making a refresh call. During this call, replace the expired access token with the refresh token in the header of the request: *Authorization: Bearer {{REFRESH_TOKEN}}*

The response to the refresh call will provide a new access token and a new refresh token. The refresh token used for this call is invalidated and added to a blacklist.

The API developed allows for high-frequency data ingestion, making it possible to track the freshness status of the product throughout its journey across the supply chain.

```

IoTdata.json
...
{
  "_id": {"$oid": "66dabf24080de65ec2652778"},
  "CH4": 7.95,
  "CO2": 893,
  "GPS": "{latitude=-6.697261, longitude=-75.341864,
  _id=66dabf24080de65ec2652779}",
  "H2S": 2.54,
  "NH3": 4.22,
  "___v": 0,
  "createdAt": {"$date": "2024-09-06T08:36:52.789Z"},
  "date": {"$date": "2024-01-09T11:46:14.000Z"},
  "deviceInternalId": "66b5d9f89f86567154dc1cf9",
  "humidity": 30.73,
  "pH": 5.28,
  "temperature": 15.01,
  "updatedAt": {"$date": "2024-09-06T08:36:52.789Z"}
}
...

```

Figure 7 - Raw IoT data API

The integration of these sensor data into the digital traceability framework contributes to improving decision-making during storage and distribution and adds transparency for downstream actors, including consumers, by enriching the information accessible through the QR codes and blockchain-anchored records.

Complete documentation is available online on <https://api.novafoodies.eu/api-docs>

3.2. RFID supply chain data

As part of the effort to ensure full digital traceability along the aquaculture supply chain, the NOVAFOODIES Market Place platform integrates a system based on RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology to track the movement of goods from the production site to the distribution network. This solution was designed to complement the traceability of batch and shipment data, reducing manual data entry and minimizing human error during logistics operations.

Each production batch, once prepared for shipment, is associated with a specific RFID tag, which contains a unique shipment identifier and is physically attached to the transport unit (e.g., pallet or container). These tags are readable by compatible RFID readers installed at key checkpoints along the distribution path—such as loading docks, logistics hubs, and warehouse entries—allowing automatic and contactless recording of the product’s movement.

The RFID data captured includes:

- Shipment code (linked to batch and product type)
- Timestamp of departure and arrival
- Geographic checkpoint (reader location)
- Carrier or logistics operator (if available)

This information is transmitted and stored in the cloud infrastructure of the MarketPlace platform and is automatically matched with the corresponding batch and QR-code traceability data. By doing so, it enables real-time monitoring of product flows, enhances the visibility of the supply chain, and strengthens traceability consistency from farm to final delivery.

The system is designed to be scalable and interoperable with existing logistics infrastructures, supporting both local and cross-border distribution scenarios. Ultimately, the RFID integration reinforces the platform's objective of offering producers and distributors a high-tech, low-effort solution for tracking the physical flow of aquaculture products in a transparent and secure way.

3.3. Production, batch and shipping supply chain data

The technical and functional design of the system for managing production, batch, and shipping data was developed through a collaborative and iterative process, based on real-world inputs from the two pilot partners: Aqua de Ma (Italy) and Kefalonia Fisheries (Greece). These companies contributed concrete information about their production processes, data availability, and operational workflows, which were collected via structured surveys and validated through multiple rounds of follow-up interviews and feedback sessions.

This iterative methodology allowed the project team to progressively refine the data model and system logic, ensuring that the platform could cover both the needs observed in the pilot cases and potential future scenarios not explicitly addressed during this initial phase. As a result, the system has been designed with maximum flexibility, supporting the management of heterogeneous production configurations and logistics setups, including varying batch sizes, certifications, and shipment frequencies.

To facilitate onboarding and usability, standardized reference data are preloaded into the system. For example, the fish species registry includes a predefined list based on FAO Alpha-3 codes, ensuring consistency with international norms and facilitating traceability alignment across borders. The data input interfaces support localization by country and language (EN, IT, EL), allowing each producer to operate in their preferred language environment while preserving data standardization at the backend.

The platform is multi-tenant and supports multi-user management. Each registered company operates in a logically isolated environment, with exclusive access to its own data. A system administrator, with appropriate credentials, may be granted access to individual company environments for monitoring or support purposes—always in accordance with predefined governance rules.

Main entities managed in the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace database are:

- Companies: company profiles with localized settings, description, contact information

3.4. Cloud Computing

The NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform has been designed to operate within a Cloud Computing infrastructure capable of ensuring high availability, scalability, cost predictability, and above all, data security and resilience. Given the strategic importance of digital traceability in the aquaculture value chain, the computing environment needed to support continuous service access, even during peak usage, while maintaining a clear structure for data segregation and secure communications.

Figure 9 - NOVAFOODIES Cloud architecture

The selected provider for the infrastructure is Amazon Web Services (AWS). AWS was chosen based on its proven track record in international R&I projects and mission-critical enterprise systems. It is already in use within the company for other high-reliability applications and offers a complete ecosystem of services for database hosting, API management, user access control, and real-time data ingestion.

The system architecture was built to support horizontal scalability, allowing resources to be scaled up or down based on real-time demand. In addition, AWS's pricing model makes it possible to estimate costs in advance, facilitating financial planning throughout the project. The infrastructure also adopts security-by-design principles, with continuous backups, access control policies, and monitoring systems that ensure the integrity and protection of stored data.

The NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform is hosted in one of the European AWS regions, ensuring that the service is easily accessible and benefits from low latency, especially for users in Italy and Greece. This geographic choice guarantees compliance with European data protection regulations and allows all project partners to interact with the system in real time, with optimal performance and reliability.

To ensure effective team collaboration and early system testing, the cloud environment was progressively deployed starting from the first months of WP6. This approach allowed developers

and stakeholders across different partners to work directly in a live production-like environment, accelerating development cycles, improving coordination, and reducing integration risks during the pilot phase.

3.5. Blockchain technology

In the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform, blockchain technology is used to securely store key data collected throughout the entire aquaculture supply chain. This includes information related to production batches, certifications, shipments, and environmental parameters captured in real time by the IoT device. By anchoring this data to the blockchain, the system ensures that it is immutable, verifiable, and transparently accessible to authorized stakeholders—adding a strong layer of trust to the digital traceability model.

At the core of this system lies the concept of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT). A DLT is a decentralized database shared across a network of nodes, where each new piece of information (a "block") is linked to the previous one, forming a chain. Once data is added and validated, it cannot be altered retroactively, which guarantees the integrity of the information and protects against fraud or manipulation.

There are two main types of blockchain architectures:

- A public blockchain is open to anyone and fully decentralized, where all transactions are visible and participants are anonymous or pseudonymous.
- A private blockchain, by contrast, is restricted to specific participants, usually managed by a consortium or a single trusted organization, offering own control, performance, and confidentiality for enterprise or research applications.

Unlike many enterprise applications that rely on private or consortium blockchains to protect confidential data, NOVAFOODIES made a deliberate choice to adopt a public blockchain infrastructure. This decision was driven by the project's fundamental goals of maximizing transparency, accessibility, and consumer trust. Since the platform does not handle any sensitive or personal data, there was no need to restrict access to the ledger. Instead, using a public blockchain makes traceability data openly available to anyone with the corresponding QR code—providing consumers with direct, independent access to the product's history and quality information.

Moreover, the choice of a public blockchain, which does not require maintenance fees or subscription costs, represents a forward-looking solution to ensure that the traceability data recorded through the NOVAFOODIES platform will remain publicly accessible and verifiable well beyond the five-year retention period typically required after the end of the project. This approach supports the long-term preservation of transparency and aligns with the principles of open data and open access, guaranteeing that the information remains available to all stakeholders—including consumers, researchers, and policy makers—without dependence on proprietary infrastructure.

The analysis of technical requirements and operational costs led our technical team to identify blockchain as a strategic technology for ensuring transparency, data immutability, and long-term sustainability in managing traceability information. After evaluating several options, Algorand was selected as the most suitable public blockchain for the project's needs.

Algorand is a next-generation public blockchain, specifically designed to overcome the limitations of earlier blockchain technologies in terms of scalability, decentralization, and environmental sustainability. Built on a Pure Proof-of-Stake (PPoS) consensus protocol, Algorand enables fast and secure transaction validation with minimal energy consumption, avoiding the inefficiencies and environmental impact typical of Proof-of-Work (PoW) systems.

As a fully decentralized and open-access ledger, Algorand guarantees transparency and security, making it ideal for projects like NOVAFOODIES that require traceability systems aligned with the principles of open data and open access. A key reason behind this choice is that the NOVAFOODIES platform does not process any sensitive or personal data, which allows the use of a public blockchain without compromising data privacy. This choice also ensures that traceability records will remain publicly accessible beyond the project's 5-year retention period, without any hosting or maintenance fees—an approach that supports long-term data preservation and public trust.

From a governance perspective, Algorand Technologies, Inc. provides development tools and technical support but does not control the network, which operates autonomously in a decentralized way. This separation reinforces the openness and neutrality required for fair and trusted supply chain traceability.

Algorand offers critical advantages for NOVAFOODIES' traceability and sustainability goals: its high scalability (thousands of TPS) ensures real-time management of supply chain data, while its energy-efficient Pure Proof-of-Stake (PPoS) mechanism minimizes environmental impact—aligning with the project's eco-conscious mission. The platform's smart contract capabilities (ASC1) enable automation of complex traceability tasks, such as logging supply chain information, with full transparency. Additionally, Algorand's interoperability and open standards simplify integration with external systems, promoting collaboration across stakeholders. Together, these features make Algorand a robust, sustainable foundation for project blockchain-based solutions. The adoption of Algorand is also fully compatible with the ISO/TR 16340:2023 technical report, which defines the requirements for blockchain-based traceability platforms in cold chain food systems. Algorand meets all key criteria outlined in the standard, including data immutability, security, energy efficiency, and system sustainability. The ability to implement smart contracts is particularly relevant, as it enables rule-based automation of traceability processes—ensuring consistency, auditability, and reliability.

Moreover, ISO/TR 16340:2023 emphasizes interoperability and openness, essential for facilitating collaboration among producers, regulators, and consumers. Algorand's architecture makes it possible to integrate the NOVAFOODIES traceability data with other monitoring systems, such as IoT devices, and supply chain databases.

The smart contract designed for the NOVAFOODIES platform allows the system to record key traceability events—such as the registration of a production batch and the logging of IoT sensor data—directly on the Algorand blockchain. It was developed using PyTeal, Algorand's smart contract language, and follows a lightweight structure to ensure efficiency and low transaction costs.

In conclusion, the decision to adopt Algorand as the blockchain infrastructure for NOVAFOODIES is consistent with both the technical goals of the project and international standards for traceability in food and aquaculture. It provides a robust, future-proof, and environmentally responsible

solution, capable of supporting transparent and trustworthy value chains in line with the EU Farm to Fork strategy and global sustainability objectives.

3.6. Market Place platform UI/UX design

The design of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform interface was developed through a structured process that combined usability principles with visual coherence, ensuring that the final user experience would be both functional and aligned with the project's identity.

Dashboard

Figure 10 - NOVAFOODIES Market Place wireframe Figma draft

The first phase of the work focused on the analysis of user requirements and navigation flows, aiming to create an intuitive interface that would support producers, distributors, and administrators in managing traceability operations efficiently. From the earliest stages, the design team ensured full alignment with the visual identity of the NOVAFOODIES project, integrating graphic elements, color palettes, and typography consistent with the official logo and communication guidelines.

USER FLOW

NOVAFOODIES I MARKET PLACE

Figure 11 - Wireframe user flow on Figma

To translate functional requirements into an accessible and user-friendly design, the team adopted an iterative design methodology using Figma, a collaborative design tool widely used in modern UI/UX workflows. The process began with the creation of wireframes, which allowed the team to define the structural layout of the main components—such as batch registration, shipment tracking, and data visualization dashboards—without focusing yet on stylistic elements.

Once the structure was validated and refined through internal reviews and stakeholder feedback, the wireframes evolved into high-fidelity mockups, incorporating visual elements and real content simulations. This approach ensured early detection of potential usability issues, and allowed developers to start working on front-end implementation with a clear and validated visual reference.

DASHBOARD - ANALYSIS

NOVAFOODIES | MARKET PLACE

Figure 12 - NOVAFOODIES Market Place dashboard mockup on Figma

The result is a digital environment that balances aesthetic coherence with functional clarity, supporting the objectives of traceability, transparency, and scalability, while offering a modern and pleasant experience for all categories of users.

BATCH REGISTRY

NOVAFOODIES | MARKET PLACE

Figure 13 - NOVAFOODIES Market Place batch registry mockup on Figma

During the internal development process, multiple design iterations were required to refine and adapt the platform. As feedback was collected from both pilot case partners and the development team, the Figma project was updated several times to reflect new insights, improve usability, and ensure alignment with technical constraints and real user needs. These updates helped guarantee that the final interface would be practical, accessible, and ready for deployment in real-world aquaculture contexts.

The complete prototype of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace, developed using Figma, is available online at the following URL link:

<https://www.figma.com/proto/PJMPjOqLr26RsKt1ywYpP3/NOVAFOODIES?page-id=423%3A25110&node-id=423-30761&viewport=1609%2C3315%2C0.38&t=W2cT5hizegV5NtdS-1&scaling=min-zoom&starting-point-node-id=423%3A36276>

Figure 14 - FIGMA prototype repository QR code

4. NOVAFOODIES MARKET PLACE DEVELOPMENT

Following the design phase, the development of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform translated the functional and technical specifications into a fully operational software environment. The work carried out during the design stage—particularly the definition of data models, API structure, and user interface wireframes—provided a solid foundation for the implementation process.

The development activities were organised in progressive phases, allowing the technical team to validate each module iteratively and ensure coherence with the objectives of transparency, traceability, and usability outlined in the project. The modular architecture of the platform enabled parallel development of key components, including batch management, shipment tracking, IoT data integration, and blockchain anchoring.

Throughout this phase, the feedback collected from pilot partners and internal testing played a crucial role in refining the system, ensuring that the platform remained consistent with real operational needs and aligned with the user experience goals defined during the UI/UX design. The following sections describe in detail how each core functionality of the platform was implemented.

4.1. Methodology

The development of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform was based on a hybrid methodology, combining elements of the Agile approach with a more structured workflow-based model, in order to adapt to the specific needs of a research and innovation project while ensuring efficiency, coordination, and progressive delivery of results.

Development activities were organised around a core technical team, composed of software developers, UI/UX designers, data architects and blockchain specialists, supported by pilot case coordinators and domain experts from the aquaculture sector. This multidisciplinary structure allowed the team to validate functionalities not only from a technical point of view, but also in terms of practical applicability and ease of use.

A key element of the methodology was the implementation of bi-weekly technical meetings, which served to align the progress of different workstreams, identify possible bottlenecks, and quickly adjust priorities. During these meetings, the team reviewed completed features, planned the next sprint, and discussed feedback collected from early tests and from the pilot partners.

The iterative nature of the Agile approach allowed the team to continuously refine and improve the platform, integrating new requirements or adjustments that emerged during the development process. At the same time, the adoption of a workflow structure helped maintain clear documentation, version control, and consistency between the various components (such as database design, API logic, blockchain interaction and front-end usability).

This balanced and flexible methodology ensured a robust and scalable implementation path, enabling the project to move forward with clarity and cohesion, while staying responsive to real-world feedback and evolving user needs.

4.2. Web application NOVAFOODIES Market Place

The NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace was developed as a cloud-based web application, designed to support the digital management and end-to-end traceability of aquaculture supply chains. The platform includes a set of integrated modules that allow users to register production batches, monitor environmental parameters collected from IoT devices, manage shipments, upload certifications, and anchor selected events to the blockchain infrastructure.

Development followed an API-first approach, meaning the backend was structured to expose clean, reusable, and well-documented APIs from the outset. This strategy allowed full decoupling of the user interface from the business logic and data layers, making the platform more flexible, scalable, and suitable for integration with other tools such as mobile applications and third-party systems.

The backend system was built using Node.js, chosen for its event-driven architecture and strong support for asynchronous operations, which facilitates the development of high-performance APIs. For data storage, the system uses MongoDB, a NoSQL document-based database. This choice was particularly well suited to the flexible and evolving nature of the traceability data model, allowing for efficient management of heterogeneous data such as batch records, sensor logs, and certification files. MongoDB also provides high scalability and native support for cloud deployments.

On the frontend, the platform was implemented with Angular, a modern web framework that enables modular UI development and dynamic rendering of content, ensuring a fast and responsive experience for all types of users. The interface was designed following the principles of usability and accessibility, and closely aligned with the visual identity of the NOVAFOODIES project.

The application architecture is fully cloud-native, deployed on Amazon Web Services (AWS) to guarantee high availability, scalability, and secure integration with external components, including IoT APIs and blockchain endpoints. The platform was developed exclusively using open-source software, adopting widely used community libraries for authentication, data visualization, form validation, and QR code generation. This approach ensures long-term maintainability and minimizes dependency on proprietary technologies.

To guarantee quality and development efficiency, a CI/CD pipeline based on GitHub was implemented, supporting structured workflows for version control, code review, automated testing, and staged deployment. Each feature is developed in isolated branches, verified through unit and integration tests, and promoted to production only after passing staging validation.

Thanks to this modular, API-first, and open-source-based approach, the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace achieves a high level of interoperability, robustness, and scalability, while fully respecting the project's guiding principles of transparency, openness, and sustainability.

4.3. RFID technology implementation

To ensure that the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace could be effectively used in real-world operational contexts, the project integrated RFID (Radio-Frequency Identification) technology into the system architecture, allowing automated tracking of product movements along the aquaculture supply chain.

The implementation required the use of dedicated RFID tags and readers. Given the maturity and widespread adoption of RFID in logistics and industrial applications, the project team selected a commercially available RFID reader equipped with built-in software and Wi-Fi internet connectivity. This choice ensured both reliability and ease of integration with the existing platform, without the need for custom hardware development.

Figure 15 - RFID reader devices and branded RFID tag

To make the system interoperable, the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace was extended with a dedicated API endpoint designed specifically for RFID-based interactions. Through this interface, the RFID

reader can communicate directly with the platform, sending information every time a tag is scanned.

When a tag is read, the system is able to:

- Identify the tag code
- Associate it with a specific production batch
- Register the date and time of the operation
- Define the type of logistics event (e.g., "departure from producer warehouse" or "arrival at customer logistics hub")

This setup allows for real-time registration of key supply chain steps and ensures traceability without relying on manual data entry, thus reducing errors and improving efficiency. The integration of RFID into the digital traceability flow further strengthens the reliability of the NOVAFOODIES Market Place system, making it suitable for everyday use by producers, logistics operators, and distributors across the aquaculture value chain.

4.4. Blockchain implementation

The international standard ISO/TR 16340:2023 recommends a blockchain implementation model that promotes a decentralized and direct data management approach by all stakeholders involved in the food value chain. In this ideal scenario, each actor—such as aquaculture producers, distributors, and dealers—would interact with the blockchain through smart contracts embedded in a Decentralized Application (dApp). This model requires every operator to directly record data on the blockchain, for instance, by logging harvest events, sales notes, or transportation and storage conditions.

However, despite its theoretical advantages, this model presents significant implementation challenges that make it impractical in the context of the NOVAFOODIES project.

The main limitations lie in the high technical complexity and operational cost associated with full decentralization. Each actor in the supply chain would need adequate IT infrastructure and specific technical skills to use the dApp and interact securely with the blockchain. This is particularly difficult for small and medium aquaculture operators, who often lack the necessary resources or digital maturity.

Moreover, integrating data from heterogeneous sources—including manual entries in the Marketplace system, IoT devices, and RFID readers—would require continuous and advanced technical coordination, resulting in high demand for time and financial resources.

To address these constraints, the INFOTEAM technical team opted for a simplified and pragmatic implementation model. Rather than relying on a fully decentralized architecture managed independently by each actor, all traceability data collected through the Marketplace system is validated and recorded on the blockchain via a central node operated directly by the project team.

This centralized gateway approach maintains the core benefits of blockchain technology, such as transparency, immutability, and verifiability, while significantly reducing the complexity and cost of deployment. Importantly, it allows for the integration of diverse data sources into a unified and trustworthy traceability framework.

In blockchain systems based on hash verification, the integrity of the information is guaranteed by recording a cryptographic fingerprint—called a hash—rather than storing the full data directly on the blockchain. This hash is generated from the original content (for example, a JSON payload that includes details like the producer’s name, company, address, and so on) using a mathematical algorithm. The result is a unique string of characters that corresponds only to that specific set of data. If even a single comma or letter in the original content changes, the resulting hash would be completely different.

In the case of the NOVAFOODIES Market Place platform, when a user generates traceability data (such as information about a batch or producer), the system calculates the hash of that information and stores it inside a blockchain transaction. This transaction acts as a time-stamped, tamper-proof certificate that the data existed exactly in that form at a specific moment.

Figure 16 - Hash string matching

To verify the authenticity of the information later, anyone can simply take the same payload, compute its hash again, and compare it to the value stored on the blockchain. If the two match perfectly, it means that the data has not been modified or corrupted. This process is both transparent and secure, and ensures that even without recording the full content on the blockchain, its integrity is preserved and publicly verifiable.

To verify that the information provided by the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App is authentic and has not been altered, simply copy the payload and paste it into a someone hash generator. If the hash result matches the one stored in the blockchain transaction, it means the data is valid and unchanged.

Transaction ID on [Algorand TestNet](#):

KCLNVP5B5QIVJ4ZXX4WODHNM074MZSREVAFXI3NRBMA2VSVHYPPQ

Payload (download [fully payload](#))

General purples [SHA256 generator website](#)

```

{"producer":{"name":"Acme","companyName":"Acme
Corp.,"iva":"3074948203544576","address":"49122 First
Street","city":"East
Electastad","state":"Spain","zipCode":"8022992158195712","country":"SX
","phone":"1-343-395-
4727","email":"Martin55@example.org","website":"https://lawful-
petticoat.com/","description":"Cornu surculus decimus. Assentator ara
cumque assumenda blanditiis. Torqueo hic candidus
nemo.,"image":"data:image/jpeg;base64,/9j/4AAQSkZJRgABAQAAQABAAD/
...
Signature=017dd581c977b1c61635dc03e35c19dc5b5f2a935a85454f6ad79e7c0430
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1","location":"Test,
2","_id":"67d0420fe3553b4b130d680c"},"properties":[{"englishName":"Eur
opean seabass","scientificName":"Dicentrarchus
labrax","nutrients":[{"nutrient":"zt","value":"20mg"}]}]}

```

Figure 17 - Example of traceability payload

Despite this simplification, the blockchain component continues to fulfil the core objectives inspired by ISO/TR 16340:2023, ensuring robust traceability for aquaculture production. The solution is designed to evolve in future phases, potentially enabling more decentralized interactions as the digital readiness of stakeholders increases.

However, blockchain technology also incurs transaction costs, as each action recorded on the blockchain requires a small fee paid in the respective cryptocurrency, commonly referred to as "gas". These costs can fluctuate significantly, with transaction fees rising unpredictably (even by more than +1000% within an hour). While Algorand currently offers relatively low transaction fees—around €0.005 per transaction—the project team recognized the potential unpredictability of these costs in a live environment.

To manage these uncertainties, the decision was made to purchase a prepaid cloud service that interacts with the blockchain, providing a flat-fee model for transactions. This service allows stable, predictable costs for writing data to the blockchain, with the average cost per transaction set at around €0.01. This approach ensures that transaction expenses remain consistent, regardless of market fluctuations, and offers the NOVAFOODIES project a more controlled and efficient way to handle blockchain transactions without exposing users to variable costs.

Additionally, by using this prepaid cloud service, INFOTEAM avoids the need to hold cryptocurrency directly, which could be subject to fluctuating market conditions and ongoing changes in tax regulations. This solution also ensures that there will be sufficient resources to register transactions on the blockchain for the entire duration of the project. Furthermore, the information stored on the Algorand blockchain will remain permanently available, even if there is no remaining credit. The data will be accessible in the public blockchain indefinitely, and it can be freely consulted well beyond the project's 5-year period of required data retention, without the need to access it through

the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App. This guarantees the long-term transparency and availability of traceability data.

4.5. Market Place internal software testing

The internal testing phase of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform was essential to validate the reliability and usability of the system before its deployment in the pilot environments. Testing activities were carried out using realistic data provided directly by the two pilot partners, Aqua de Ma and Kefalonia Fisheries, including actual batch records, production sites, and logistics scenarios. This allowed the technical team to simulate real use cases and identify potential improvements in data structure and user workflows.

In addition to technical validations, the platform was tested internally by non-technical personnel, simulating the experience of real users. These tests were conducted using the actual equipment provided for the project, such as the IoT device and RFID readers for tracking shipments.

Figure 18 - IoT device data simulation

Tests were also conducted using the multi-user environment provided by the software, with different roles and access levels for producers, operators and administrators. For all blockchain-related operations, the system was connected to the Algorand TestNet, ensuring a safe and cost-free environment to validate data anchoring, without interacting with the real MainNet during the development phase.

To monitor transactions, accounts, and smart contracts on the Algorand blockchain, you can use the official explorer services. Below are the direct links to both the MainNet and TestNet explorers.

This environment is intended for testing and development purposes. You can explore TestNet transactions and smart contract simulations via:

- <https://testnet.algo.surf/>

Use this link to view activity on the official live Algorand blockchain network:

- <https://algo.surf/explorer>

These platforms provide detailed insights into blocks, transactions, assets, and account states, and are essential tools for both developers and stakeholders in the Algorand ecosystem.

Figure 19 - Algorand blockchain TestNet explorer

This approach allowed the team to assess not only system stability and accuracy of the data flows, but also the overall ease of use and accessibility of the interface, leading to useful feedback that guided the final refinements of the platform.

5. NOVAFOODIES MOBILE APP DESIGN

Alongside the development of the B2B MarketPlace platform, the NOVAFOODIES project also focused on designing a dedicated mobile app for end consumers, aimed at providing easy and transparent access to seafood traceability information.

The app was specifically designed with the understanding that it will be used by a wide and diverse audience, potentially spanning all age groups and varying levels of digital literacy. For this reason, the user interface was developed to be simple, intuitive, and accessible, even for non-technical

users. Special attention was given to the user experience, particularly in the QR code scanning process and the clear presentation of key product information such as production location, environmental quality indicators, and certifications.

The interface was also standardized to support development for both Google® Android® and Apple® iOS® operating systems, ensuring broad compatibility and facilitating future deployment across major mobile platforms.

The goal of the mobile app is to offer a seamless and trustworthy experience, helping consumers quickly access verified traceability data and reinforcing confidence in sustainable aquaculture products across the European market.

5.1. Labelling and QR code technologies

As part of the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App, a dedicated labelling system was designed to support the additional, voluntary traceability layer offered through the platform, without interfering with the existing mandatory traceability practices already in place for aquaculture producers and retailers. The goal was to provide consumers with transparent and verifiable information through a parallel and complementary channel, while respecting current regulatory frameworks and commercial workflows.

For this reason, the design of the label followed a minimalist and essential approach, ensuring that it could be easily integrated at points of sale—such as fish counters or display shelves—without generating confusion or overlap with official product labelling. Each label includes only the core elements strictly necessary to activate the traceability experience: a short slogan to invite interaction “*KNOW WHAT YOU EAT*”, a QR code, its associated alphanumeric code (for manual entry if needed), the name of the producer, and a clear reference to the NOVAFOODIES project.

Figure 20 - NOVAFOODIES traceability label

The labels were also designed to ensure optimal readability of the QR code at the typical distance between a consumer's smartphone and the fish counter. This ensures that the scanning process is quick, intuitive, and technically reliable in real retail environments, contributing to a seamless and engaging user experience.

Figure 21 - Traceability label usage - AI generated image

By balancing clarity, discretion, and functionality, the NOVAFOODIES label system reinforces the project's objective of building consumer trust without imposing changes on producers or commercial operators, and without altering the legal traceability chain already in place.

5.2. Traceability information using Mobile Application

Through the NOVAFOODIES Mobile Application, consumers can easily access complete traceability information about the seafood products they are purchasing by simply scanning the QR code displayed on the product label. This transparent system allows users to view detailed information about the product's journey from the producer to the point of sale, ensuring full visibility of its quality and origin.

The information available includes:

- Complete producer details: Consumers can learn about the producer's name, company profile, and location, providing context about where the product originated.
- Production batch information: The app displays detailed data on the production batch, including the seeding process, helping consumers understand the product's journey through the supply chain.
- Production sites: Information about the production sites includes location, key characteristics, photos, and the production methodology used (e.g., offshore and open water farming, closed systems, or integrated multi-trophic aquaculture), offering a complete view of the environment in which the product was grown.
- Certifications: The app provides details about process certifications, sustainability certifications, and guarantees such as Non-GMO (Genetically Modified Organisms) and antibiotic-free production, giving consumers assurance of the product's quality and adherence to environmental and health standards.
- Nutritional values and laboratory analyses: Consumers can also access nutritional information and the results of laboratory tests, ensuring that the seafood products meet high-quality standards for safety, taste, and nutritional value.

This comprehensive, transparent traceability system empowers consumers by providing them with the detailed, verified information they need to make informed decisions about the products they consume, fostering greater trust in the aquaculture sector and its commitment to sustainability and quality.

Figure 22 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile APP explained

The data collected from the IoT devices play a crucial role in ensuring the transparency and safety of seafood products throughout the supply chain, particularly during transportation. The IoT devices monitor and record key environmental parameters, such as temperature, humidity, and ammonia levels, all of which are critical for ensuring that the biosecurity conditions required for proper storage and transport are met.

This real-time data is collected and transmitted to the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform through API integration, allowing continuous monitoring of the product's conditions as it moves from the producer's warehouse to the logistics platform and ultimately to the retailer. By collecting and storing this data in the blockchain, the system guarantees that the information is immutable and auditable, providing a tamper-proof record of the product's journey.

For consumers, this traceability system offers enhanced transparency. Using the mobile app, they can view a map representation that shows the entire delivery path of the product, from the producer's warehouse to the logistics platform, ensuring that all the necessary conditions for safe transport and storage were maintained. This feature allows consumers to verify that the products they purchase have been handled according to the required biosecurity standards, giving them confidence in the quality and safety of their seafood.

Figure 23 - Delivery GPS map

5.3. Mobile Application UI/UX design

The design of the NOVAFOODIES mobile application followed a structured and iterative approach, clearly distinguishing between the User Experience (UX) and User Interface (UI) design phases. The entire process was carried out using Figma, a collaborative design tool that enabled the team to visualize, share, and refine the app concept from early sketches to final visual mockups.

In the UX design phase, the focus was on defining the structure, flow, and user interactions within the application. Starting from wireframes, the team identified the essential user paths—such as QR

code scanning, viewing product traceability details, and accessing validation tools. Special attention was given to creating a navigation system that would be intuitive for all users, regardless of age or digital familiarity. This phase involved defining the overall workflow, ensuring the app could deliver information clearly and with minimal effort from the user.

Once the experience flow was validated, the UI design phase concentrated on the visual aspects of the application. The mockups were designed using the graphic identity of the NOVAFOODIES project, including the official color palette, typography, and logo. This ensured strong coherence with the overall branding. The interface was optimized for clarity, accessibility, and cross-platform compatibility, targeting both Android® and iOS® devices from the beginning.

Figure 24 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile APP mockup on Figma

The entire design process required several iterations, during which both UX and UI elements were revised and improved. Feedback was collected from technical teams, project stakeholders, and pilot case partners, allowing the design to evolve and align with practical needs and user expectations.

The final result is a multilingual application (available in English, Italian, and Greek) offering a smooth and engaging user experience. Through QR code scanning, consumers can easily access product traceability details, including origin, farming methods, certifications, and producer

information. Additionally, the app includes a guided feature that allows users to verify the authenticity of blockchain-anchored data, further enhancing transparency and trust in the aquaculture value chain.

The complete prototype of the NOVAFOODIES Mobile App, developed using Figma, is available online at the following URL link:

<https://www.figma.com/proto/PJMPjOqLr26RsKt1ywYpP3/NOVAFOODIES?page-id=233%3A17651&node-id=233-19724&viewport=629%2C881%2C0.16&t=Baj4iQzksCitGfsH-1&scaling=scale-down&content-scaling=fixed&starting-point-node-id=233%3A19693>

5.4. Poster and Landing Page

To support the dissemination and real-world use of the NOVAFOODIES mobile application, a dedicated landing page was designed to host the download links and installation instructions for the app. The page offers users a quick and intuitive way to access the application, regardless of the device or operating system used, and has been localized in three languages—Italian and Greek, corresponding to the countries involved in the pilot cases, and English, which is always available to ensure accessibility for a broader international audience.

Figure 25 - NOVAFOODIES landing page on Figma

This landing page can be accessed by scanning a specific QR code printed on a series of promotional posters, which were also developed as part of the project’s communication materials. These posters will be displayed in all fish shops and retail markets participating in the pilot, where products traced through the NOVAFOODIES platform are available.

KNOW WHAT YOU EAT

Fish supply chain traceability at your fingertips,
for an informed and conscious choice.

NOVAFOODIES GET THE MOBILE APP

Download on the App Store

GET IT ON Google Play

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This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 101084180.

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Figure 26 - NOVAFOODIES poster store (English version)

The posters are designed to be visually clear, engaging, and informative, following the official NOVAFOODIES visual identity. They include a call-to-action inviting consumers to scan the QR code

to “*KNOW WHAT YOU EAT*” like the landing page, the posters are also localized in Italian, Greek, and English, ensuring that they are fully understandable by local customers while remaining accessible to any international consumer.

This coordinated communication strategy—combining physical presence at the point of sale with digital access tools—aims to encourage consumer interaction and reinforce the project’s values of traceability, transparency, and trust in the aquaculture value chain.

5.5. Consumers personal data

The NOVAFOODIES mobile application has been designed following the principles of privacy by design, with a strong emphasis on minimizing data collection and ensuring full compliance with the project’s Data Management Plan. In line with this approach, and considering that there is no practical or functional need to collect personal information from end users, the app does not require any form of account registration.

Consumers will be able to freely access and use the application anonymously, without providing names, emails, or any other identifying information. The entire user experience—from scanning a QR code to viewing traceability information—has been structured to function without storing or processing personal data on the platform or on the cloud infrastructure.

This approach is fully consistent with the provisions of the NOVAFOODIES Grant Agreement, which does not foresee the processing of personal data for the end-user application, and is explicitly confirmed in the Data Management Plan of the project, where it is stated that no personal data will be collected, stored, or processed through the consumer mobile app.

6. NOVAFOODIES MOBILE APP DEVELOPMENT

The development of the NOVAFOODIES mobile application focused on creating a seamless and accessible experience for end users across both Google® Android® and Apple® iOS® platforms. To achieve this, a unified framework was adopted, leveraging the React Native language, which allowed for efficient development and deployment on both systems while maintaining consistency in functionality and user interface. This approach minimized the need for separate development efforts for each platform, reducing time and resources while ensuring a high-quality app experience for all users. In the following sections, we will detail the key development stages, testing procedures, and final deployment of the app.

6.1. Mobile Application for Google® Android®

The development of the NOVAFOODIES mobile application for Google® Android® began with the creation of initial mockups and UI designs, which were aligned with the project’s visual identity and focused on ensuring a clean and user-friendly interface. The React Native framework was chosen to develop the app, allowing for efficient cross-platform functionality while maintaining a native experience on Android® devices.

The technical development involved integrating necessary APIs to enable seamless communication between the mobile app and the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform. This integration allowed the app to retrieve and display traceability data, such as product origin, farming methods, and

certifications, in real time. Special attention was given to optimizing the API calls to ensure fast data retrieval and minimal latency for users.

Throughout the development, the code was continuously optimized to improve performance, ensuring smooth interaction with the backend and efficient management of app resources. Key optimizations included reducing memory usage, ensuring fast loading times, and improving battery efficiency, all crucial factors for enhancing the user experience on mobile devices.

Figure 27 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile App (1.0) running on Android smartphone

By focusing on both technical robustness and design clarity, Android app was designed to be highly responsive, ensuring users could easily access traceability information with minimal interaction. The integration of real-time data from the NOVAFOODIES Market Place platform further strengthened

the app's functionality, enabling users to trust and rely on the app for accurate, transparent product information.

6.2. Mobile Application for Apple® iOS®

The development of the NOVAFOODIES mobile application for Apple® iOS® followed a similar approach to the Android® version, but with additional challenges due to the more restrictive nature of the iOS® operating system. iOS® requires stricter guidelines for app performance, privacy, and security, which necessitated careful attention to meet Apple's standards for App Store submission.

The first phase involved creating the UI mockups and ensuring they aligned with the overall design of the NOVAFOODIES project, taking into consideration iOS-specific design principles, such as navigation patterns and visual clarity. Despite these additional constraints, the app was developed using React Native, allowing the use of a shared codebase across both platforms, while optimizing the app specifically for iOS® devices to maintain the native performance and smooth user experience that iOS® users expect.

One of the primary technical difficulties in iOS development was the integration of the necessary APIs for seamless communication with the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform. Unlike Android®, iOS® imposes more stringent background process restrictions and data-fetching limitations, which required additional effort to ensure reliable API communication and efficient real-time data synchronization. To address these challenges, the app's API calls were optimized for low-latency responses, and special care was taken to comply with iOS's background task limitations without compromising the user experience.

Another significant hurdle was meeting the privacy and security standards required by Apple®. Given the nature of the data (traceability, product origin, and certifications), the app needed to be fully compliant with Apple's App Store policies, which involved extra scrutiny on data handling and user consent procedures. The application was developed with privacy-by-design principles and integrated secure authentication methods to safeguard user data.

Figure 28 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile App (1.0) running on iPhone 13

Finally, the iOS version of the app underwent a rigorous testing process, including performance checks on different Apple® devices (iPhones and iPads), ensuring that the app performed well across various screen sizes and configurations, while maintaining high standards of battery efficiency, loading speed, and overall stability.

Through careful adaptation to the unique constraints of iOS, the NOVAFOODIES app was able to deliver a seamless, secure, and fully functional experience, meeting both user expectations and platform-specific requirements.

6.3. Google Play Store and Apple® App Store

As part of the final phase of mobile app development, it was essential to create dedicated app listings on both the Google® Play Store and Apple® App Store to ensure the app's visibility and

accessibility to consumers. This process involved several assessment steps, where all necessary details were carefully outlined and presented for both platforms to ensure a smooth publication.

Initially, the key functionalities of the app were clearly defined, including the target audience, the type of application (free, mobile-first, anonymous), and the compatible devices, ensuring seamless performance across both Android® and iOS® operating systems. Additionally, screenshots were prepared to give potential users a visual preview of the app's interface and its capabilities.

Figure 29 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile APP Apple App Store page

The app was then published under the INFOTEAM company developer profiles on both stores, benefiting from the company over 10 years of experience in mobile app development. INFOTEAM ensured that the app adhered to each store's guidelines for approval, ensuring technical compliance and quality assurance.

NOVAFOODIES

INFOTEAM SRL

10+ Download 3

Install

About this app →

The app, by scanning a QR code, allows you to view a lot of information on fish products traced through the Novafoodies platform. It is possible to view:

- the name of the product
- the description of the product
- the producer
- the shipping date...

Last Updated
7 apr 2025

Figure 30 - NOVAFOODIES Mobile APP Google Play Store page

Furthermore, through the Google® Play Store and Apple® App Store, subsequent versions of the mobile application will be released, following the initial development phase. Each release will be accompanied by release notes, documenting the new features, improvements, and bug fixes in every updated version, ensuring users are informed and the development process remains transparent. This versioning system allows for continuous improvement and support, keeping the app up to date and aligned with the needs of both users and stakeholders.

Google LLC and Apple Inc. are not responsible for the application and shall have no liability whatsoever in connection with its use or performance. The application is independently developed and maintained by INFOTEAM srl.

6.4. Mobile App internal software testing

The internal software testing of the NOVAFOODIES mobile App was conducted in several stages to ensure a high-quality, user-friendly experience for all potential users. The testing process involved running the app on a range of devices compatible with both Android® and iOS® operating systems, to ensure full compatibility and responsiveness across various screen sizes and hardware configurations.

A key feature of the testing process was the involvement of non-technical personnel, simulating real users with varying levels of familiarity with technology. This approach allowed the team to gather valuable feedback on the usability and intuitiveness of the app, which is crucial for an application aimed at a wide and diverse audience.

NOVAFOODIES ▾ [Distributions](#) [TestFlight](#) [Xcode Cloud](#)

Build
iOS

Feedback sui crash
Includes feedback only from testers using iOS 13, visionOS 1.0, or macOS 12 or later.

Feedback
Crash
Screenshot

Tester
Tutti

INTERNAL TESTS +
NU NovaFoodies User
TE TESTER

EXTERNAL TESTS +

Others
Informazioni per i test

DATA ▾	BUILD	DEVICE M...	VERSI...	COMMENT
Mar 14, 2025 at 10:17 AM	1.0.0 ...	iPad (5th generation)	iOS 1...	I tried to open the QR scan
Mar 14, 2025 at 9:24 AM	1.0.0 ...	iPad (5th generation)	iOS 1...	
Mar 14, 2025 at 9:24 AM	1.0.0 ...	iPad (5th generation)	iOS 1...	I scanned a QR code
Feb 12, 2025 at 6:36 PM	1.0.0 ...	iPhone 13	iOS 1...	It freezes and crashes ❌
Feb 12, 2025 at 4:15 PM	1.0.0 ...	iPhone 15	iOS 1...	I was searching for a product code manually
Feb 12, 2025 at 4:10 PM	1.0.0 ...	iPhone 13	iOS 1...	

Figure 31 - Apple TestFlight program for external tester

After successfully completing the internal testing phase of the Alpha version, the app was released on the Google® Play Store and Apple® App Store for pilot testing. During this phase, the app was shared (invited) with pilot cases partners Aqua de Ma and Kefalonia Fisheries, who were actively involved in testing the app in real-world conditions. Their feedback was essential in identifying any functional issues, user interface improvements, or areas for optimization.

All reported issues and suggestions were carefully reviewed, and necessary bug fixes and improvements will be implemented in future releases. The feedback gathered from the pilot partners helped refine the app and ensure that the final version released to the public would meet the project's goals of transparency, ease of use, and operational reliability. The iterative testing process ensured that the mobile app would be ready for mass deployment and adoption by consumers across the European market.

7. NOVAFOODIES EQUIPMENT FOR TRIALS

The successful implementation of the NOVAFOODIES traceability system in real-world conditions required the provision of specific equipment and tools to support the pilot trials conducted with Aqua de Ma and Kefalonia Fisheries. This chapter outlines the various traceability kits and associated devices supplied to the pilot partners, including advanced IoT systems, RFID technology, and QR code labels, designed to monitor, track, and document key supply chain events. The deployment of these tools was essential for testing the functionality of the NOVAFOODIES platform, ensuring seamless integration across production, logistics, and consumer touchpoints, while providing critical data to assess the effectiveness and reliability of the solution.

7.1. Traceability kit for trials

As part of the NOVAFOODIES project, dedicated traceability kits were specifically developed and provided to the pilot partners to support the experimental phase of the project. These kits contained essential tools and materials designed to implement and test the digital traceability systems within real-world aquaculture environments. The kits were tailored to the specific needs of each partner, Aqua de Ma in Italy and Kefalonia Fisheries in Greece.

Figure 32 - NOVAFOODIE kit for fish stores

For Aqua de Ma, the kit included:

- 100 promotional posters featuring the NOVAFOODIES mobile app, with multilingual options in Italian to raise consumer awareness at points of sale.
- 5000 pre-printed NOVAFOODIES QR code labels for product traceability, to be placed on the seafood products.

- 200 label display stands to ensure the QR codes were visible and easily accessible to consumers.
- 100 RFID adhesive labels for product tagging, allowing easy tracking of items in the supply chain.
- 2 RFID readers with Wi-Fi connection (mobile router and 4G SIM) to scan the RFID tags and log data for seamless integration into the NOVAFOODIES platform.
- 1 NOVAFOODIES IoT device from ITENE to monitor and record key environmental parameters, such as temperature and ammonia levels, in real-time as part of the traceability system.

Figure 33 - Pre-printed NOVAFOODIES QR code labels

For Kefalonia Fisheries, the kit included:

- 100 promotional posters (in Greek) to inform consumers about the traceability initiative.
- 5000 pre-printed NOVAFOODIES QR code labels for the fish products, allowing consumers to scan and view traceability information.
- 200 label display stands for positioning the QR code labels in an optimal way at points of sale.

No IoT and RFID devices was provided for this partner, as they were not involved in real-time environmental monitoring.

Figure 34 - Pre-printed NOVAFOODIES kit ready for shipping

These traceability kits were crucial for the success of the pilot phase, enabling the partners to collect, manage, and test the traceability data from production to consumer-facing transparency. By integrating RFID technology, QR code labels, and IoT devices, the kits ensured that all the necessary tools were available for real-time tracking and data collection. The data gathered from the trials would help fine-tune the NOVAFOODIES platform, ensuring it meets the needs of the aquaculture industry and enhances consumer trust in the sustainability and quality of seafood products.

7.2. Communication material for trials

For the success of the NOVAFOODIES project trial phase, a series of communication materials were developed to inform both dealers and consumers about the digital traceability system and its benefits. These materials aimed to raise awareness, ensure clear messaging, and encourage active participation in the trial.

The posters included in the kits were designed to be displayed in fish shops and retail locations, where they would be prominently visible to consumers. The posters carried a concise call-to-action, inviting consumers to scan the QR code on the seafood products. By scanning the code, consumers could access detailed traceability information about the product's origin, farming methods, certifications, and environmental impact. This made the process of verifying the product's transparency quick and intuitive. The posters also contained a brief overview of the NOVAFOODIES

initiative, emphasizing the value of traceability and its role in building consumer trust in aquaculture products.

ΓΝΩΡΙΣΕ ΤΙ ΤΡΩΣ

Η ιχνηλασιμότητα της αλυσίδας εφοδιασμού ψαριών στα χέρια σας, για μια ενημερωμένη και συνειδητή επιλογή

Εγκαταστήστε την εφαρμογή

Σαρώστε τον κωδικό QR

Ανακαλύψτε

NOVAFOODIES ΕΓΚΑΤΑΣΤΗΣΤΕ ΤΗΝ ΕΦΑΡΜΟΓΗ

Λήψη στο
App Store

ΑΠΟΚΤΗΣΤΕ ΤΟ ΣΤΟ
Google Play

Με τη συγχρηματοδότηση της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης

[X](#)
[in](#)
[@](#)

Figure 35 - NOVAFOODIES poster store for Greece version

In addition to the posters, the project provided draft letters to partners to help communicate the initiative to both dealers and consumers. These letters were tailored to ensure clear communication with key stakeholders and encourage active engagement.

The letter to dealers offered specific guidance on how to introduce the NOVAFOODIES traceability system in their stores. It recommended that dealers display the posters in high-traffic areas of their shops and make the QR code labels visible and easily accessible next to the seafood products. The letter emphasized the benefits for dealers, including the potential to enhance brand reputation, increase consumer confidence, and demonstrate commitment to sustainability and transparency in their product offerings.

Figure 36 - NOVAFOODIES label display stand

The letter to partners Aqua de Ma and Kefalonia Fisheries explained the key objectives of the pilot phase and the operational support required from them. It highlighted the need to actively engage with their commercial networks, distribute the traceability kits, and ensure proper communication about the initiative. This letter also provided guidance on how to effectively use the communication materials, encouraging pilot partners to engage their retail partners and make sure that staff are

well-informed about the benefits of the NOVAFOODIES system, ultimately helping drive consumer participation.

Together, these communication materials were designed to maximize the impact of the project by ensuring that both dealers and consumers were fully informed about the traceability system, and were actively engaged in using the app. The use of QR codes, informative posters, and clear messaging helped reinforce the goals of transparency, trust, and sustainability in the aquaculture value chain.

8. EXPERIMENTAL PHASE

The experimental phase of the NOVAFOODIES project was a critical step in validating the solutions developed during the design and development stages. The primary goal was to launch this phase as quickly as possible, ensuring approximately 12 months of real-world testing to gather valuable user feedback and measure the impact of the digital traceability system in the aquaculture industry.

The earlier sections of this chapter describe the planning and deployment of key components such as the MarketPlace platform and the mobile apps, which were made available for internal testing and then released for pilot partner evaluation. Special attention was given to the timing of the mobile app releases and the coordination with pilot partners to ensure smooth implementation in real-world conditions.

By prioritizing an early start to the trial phase, the project aimed to create an environment where both technical performance and user engagement could be closely monitored, allowing for necessary adjustments and refinements to be made over the course of the 12-month period. This approach was essential for the successful evaluation of the project's goals and for ensuring long-term sustainability and trust in the solutions developed.

8.1. Trials planning and production test

The experimental phase of the NOVAFOODIES project followed a structured timeline, with key milestones and deliverables guiding the development and testing. The first version of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace was already available in month M18, as outlined in the project's timeline.

Figure 37 - NOVAFOODIES experimental phase timeline

The Alpha version of the NOVAFOODIES mobile App for both Android® and iOS® was released in February 2025 for internal testing, followed by the beta version for pilot partners at the end of

March 2025. The mobile apps will officially be available for public download on the Google® Play Store and Apple® App Store starting in April 2025, completing the launch of the digital traceability system.

As agreed with the pilot partners, the launch of the NOVAFOODIES mobile app was initially planned for early April 2025. However, due to the involvement of their distribution and sales networks, it was determined that this would not be an optimal time for the public release, as the Easter holidays (on April 19, 2025, coinciding with both Catholic and Orthodox Easter) would significantly impact retail operations and consumer engagement in Italy and Greece. Consequently, the launch was rescheduled to immediately after the Easter period, ensuring that the apps would be available for download at a time when consumer access and retailer participation could be maximized.

8.2. Market Place platform deployment

The deployment of the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace platform followed a CI/CD (Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment) approach to ensure a streamlined and efficient delivery process. By utilizing a GitHub-based pipeline, the development team was able to automate the entire process of code integration, testing, and deployment, ensuring that every code change was consistently validated and seamlessly transitioned to production.

The CI pipeline started with automated code commits in GitHub, which triggered a series of steps including unit tests, integration tests, and build processes. These stages ensured that the platform's functionality remained stable and bug-free, reducing the risk of errors in the live environment. The automated testing also enabled the team to address potential issues early in the development process, promoting faster delivery and higher code quality.

Once the code successfully passed all tests, it was automatically deployed to the cloud infrastructure on AWS using a CD pipeline. The platform was built to take full advantage of AWS cloud services, ensuring scalability, security, and high availability. This architecture allowed the NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace to handle dynamic scaling, automatically adjusting to traffic increases as more users engaged with the platform.

With this CI/CD methodology, the NOVAFOODIES team could deliver updates and new features rapidly, while maintaining high performance and reliability. This approach provided a robust, agile deployment process, ensuring that the platform could continuously evolve, adapting to feedback and new requirements efficiently.

The online NOVAFOODIES Market Place is available online at: <https://backoffice.novafoodies.eu/>

A multilingual landing page is available online at: <https://landing.novafoodies.eu>

The API cloud services for communication with IoT devices are operational and are currently gathering test data online at: <https://api.novafoodies.eu/>

8.3. Mobile APPs deployment

The deployment of the NOVAFOODIES mobile apps on Google® Play Store and Apple® App Store followed a structured process. After internal testing and pilot partner feedback, the apps were submitted for review on both platforms. The Android® app was published on the Google® Play Store, ensuring compliance with Android-specific requirements, while the iOS® app was submitted to the

Apple® App Store, meeting Apple’s strict performance, privacy, and security standards. Both apps were designed with multilingual support (English, Italian, and Greek) and were made available for public download. A feedback system was integrated to continuously gather user insights for future updates and improvements, ensuring the apps stay up-to-date and functional.

- NOVAFOODIES App download for Google® Android®:
<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.eu.novafoodies>
- NOVAFOODIES App download for Apple® iOS®:
<https://apps.apple.com/it/app/novafoodies/id6741156689>

CONCLUSION

The NOVAFOODIES Market Place and App has successfully progressed towards its goal of achieving Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 8 by the end of the project. Initially, the project started at TRL 5, meaning that the NOVAFOODIES platform and mobile app were at a validation stage in a relevant environment. At this level, the technology had demonstrated its core functionalities, but it was still in the process of being tested and optimized in a controlled, experimental setting.

By the end of the project, the goal was to reach TRL 8, indicating that the system would be fully demonstrated and operational in a real-world environment. Achieving TRL 8 means the technology would be successfully deployed in live, operational settings, with the platform and app integrated into the production and distribution workflows of the pilot sites. It would also signify that the solution has undergone comprehensive testing and proven its ability to scale and operate effectively, meeting both user needs and project objectives.

At TRL 8, the NOVAFOODIES Market Place and App will be ready for commercial deployment, offering a reliable, scalable solution for digital traceability in the aquaculture sector. The platform will be capable of seamlessly integrating data from IoT devices, ensuring real-time monitoring, and utilizing blockchain technology for data integrity and transparency across the supply chain. By then, the system will have met the operational requirements for user-friendly access to traceability data and will have proven its value in enhancing consumer trust and promoting sustainability in aquaculture.

This achievement will mark a significant milestone for the project, demonstrating how digital innovations like blockchain and IoT can transform the seafood supply chain, aligning with European strategies such as Farm to Fork. The project's success at TRL 8 will pave the way for INFOTEAM to explore new opportunities in the growing field of aquaculture traceability, positioning the company for future advancements and commercial applications.

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